

FOREST REGENERATION WITH BIODIVERSE PLANTATIONS

1. Forest area destroyed by a forest fire in Galicia (NW Spain) 2. (image group) Seedlings for forest regeneration in Galicia. 3. (image group) Activities carried out during the forest regeneration.

THE WHAT AND WHY:

In recent decades, the occurrence of extreme climatic events such as storms, floods, or forest fires has had a wide-ranging impact not only on ecosystems but also on the economy, human health, and well-being. Therefore, developing innovative intervention techniques for forest regeneration is crucial, particularly those that offer solutions to accelerate forest regrowth after extreme events and create a more stable and resilient forest structure. In this context, the careful selection of tree species for forest regeneration is essential, especially when an agroforestry strategy is adopted to address the damage caused by extreme climatic events. Within the framework of the LIFE VAIA project, the establishment of different perennial (*Taxus baccata*, *Quercus ilex*, *Quercus suber*, *Pinus pinaster*) and non-perennial (*Castanea sativa*, *Quercus robur*, *Sorbus aria*, *Betula alba*, *Quercus pyrenaica*, *Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Prunus avium*) forest tree species was evaluated in a forest area in Galicia (NW Spain) that was destroyed by a forest fire.

Keywords: Forest fires, biomass, autochthonous breeds, Celtic pig, animal welfare, digitalisation, Pavlov reflex

HOW IS THE CHALLENGE ADDRESSED

How to do a forest regeneration with biodiverse plantations?

Successful forest regeneration after an extreme climatic event requires the careful selection of tree species adapted to the site's edaphoclimatic conditions. This strategy is fundamental to ensuring the long-term conservation of biodiversity and the maintenance of soil health. Moreover, species selection should also consider ecological, socioeconomic and cultural factors to enhance multifunctionality. Taking these considerations into account, and within the framework of the LIFE VAIA project, a fire-affected area in Galicia was restored with perennial and non-perennial species suited to Atlantic-Mediterranean conditions, intercropped to increase the landscape value. *Prunus avium*, *Acer pseudoplatanus*, and *Betula alba* showed the best establishment and are recommended for restoring similar climatic transitional zones due to their resilience and ecological value.

Watch videos and access extra material at:

af4eu.eu

Funded by
the European Union

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

The forest regeneration after an extreme climatic event brings two relevant advantages. On the one hand, it enables income generation for forest owners, helping to offset the losses caused by forest devastation. This income can arise in the medium to long term, once the forest begins to produce wood products again. However, it is important to highlight that herbaceous species and shrubs in the understorey can also generate income in the short, medium, and long term when agroforestry systems are implemented. In general, income is a key incentive for forest owners to ensure the maintenance and management of forests, while also enhancing ecosystem services.

On the other hand, forest regeneration enhances biodiversity, which can contribute to increasing populations of wild fauna such as small mammals and birds, as well as to halting and reversing the decline of pollinators. The expected outcome is an improved forest compared to the one that existed before the destructive event, more resilient to climate change, thanks to more complex ecosystems and greater genetic variability.

HIGHLIGHTS:

- **Successful regeneration after an extreme climatic event depends on selecting tree species adapted to local edaphoclimatic conditions.**
- **Careful species selection ensures long-term biodiversity conservation and soil health.**
- **Integrating ecological, socioeconomic, and cultural factors enhances multifunctionality in regenerated forests.**

Forest regeneration after a forest fire in Galicia (NW Spain).

More information online: www.lifevaia.eu

NURIA FERREIRO DOMÍNGUEZ, FRANCISCO JAVIER RODRÍGUEZ-RIGUEIRO, JOSÉ JAVIER SANTIAGO-FREIJANES, ANA COUSO-VIANA, MARÍA ROSA MOSQUERA LOSADA

University of Santiago de Compostela (USC)
mrosa.mosquera.losada@usc.es

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.